

Traces of Advaita Vedānta in Balinese Hindu Theo-philosophy: A Hermeneutic Approach

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the traces of Advaita Vedānta teachings in Hindu theo-philosophy in Bali through a hermeneutic approach. The non-dualistic doctrine rooted in Śaṅkara's thought has undergone transformation and adaptation within the Balinese local discourse, both textually and in religious practice. *Tattwa* manuscripts such as *Tattwa Jñāna*, *Bhuwana Kosa*, and *Tuturan Bhatāra Rsi Agastya* demonstrate a strong presence of the principle of unity between Ātman and Brahman, though expressed through symbolic and culturally distinct Balinese language. This research finds that the Advaita concept is not merely a metaphysical doctrine, but also shapes the ethical and ecological consciousness of Balinese society, as reflected in the principles of *rwa bhineda*, *Tri Hita Karana*, and the balance between *sekala-niskala*. Through a Gadamerian hermeneutic approach that emphasizes the fusion of horizons, the role of tradition, and the historicity of understanding, complemented by Ricoeur's symbolic hermeneutics, the interpretation of Advaita texts and practices becomes not merely textual, but a dialogical and contextual process that discloses symbolic meanings continually negotiated within socio-cultural realities. These findings affirm that Advaita in Bali is not an imitation of India but a localized form of spiritual universality embedded within tradition. This research contributes to the strengthening of local Hindu philosophy while also offering spiritual reflections relevant to addressing global existential and ecological crises.

Keywords: Advaita Vedānta, hermeneutics, *rwa bhineda*, *Tri Hita Karana*

Introduction

Advaita Vedānta, a key philosophical school within Hinduism, teaches that there is no real duality between the individual self (Ātman) and the ultimate reality (Brahman). Popularized by Śrī Ādi Śaṅkarācārya in the 8th century CE, this philosophy asserts that liberation (mokṣa) comes through realizing the non-dual nature of existence—that all distinctions are illusory (māyā) and Ātman is, in essence, Brahman (Mueller, 1884).

In Bali, a major Hindu cultural center outside India, Advaita Vedānta has been adapted into local beliefs and practices. Although not always presented in doctrinal terms, its non-dualistic essence appears in cultural concepts like *tat tvam asi*, *rwa bhineda*, and *sekala–niskala*. These ideas reflect a lived philosophy that resonates with Advaita thought. For example, *rwa bhineda*, meaning "two opposites in harmony," mirrors Advaita's view that apparent differences are ultimately part of a unified reality. Geertz (1973) observed that Balinese society often symbolizes the world through such harmonized dualities, suggesting that Advaita is more than metaphysical theory—it is embodied in daily life and rituals.

This philosophical presence is evident in sacred Balinese texts. *Tattwa Jñāna*, *Bhuwana Kosa*, and *Sarasamuscaya* contain teachings that align closely with Advaita principles. In *Tattwa Jñāna*, for instance, the soul (*ātman*) is described as formless and pure, identical to the divine (*paramātma*)—echoing Śaṅkara's view of *nirguṇa Brahman* (Deutsch, 1980). These parallels show that while the terminology may differ, the underlying metaphysics of non-duality are present.

Only a limited number of studies have examined these concepts through a hermeneutical perspective. Hermeneutics—the interpretive discipline that studies texts and symbols—reveals the ways in which Balinese Hindu philosophy maintains profound links with Advaita. Gadamer (2004) argued that interpretation is never a simple reproduction of meaning but rather a dynamic encounter shaped by cultural and historical context. Seen in this light, sacred writings and ritual practices in Bali can be understood as ongoing reinterpretations of Indian Vedānta within a living cultural environment.

The well-known phrase *tat tvam asi* ("you are that") carries significant weight in Bali. Far beyond being a philosophical dictum, it is employed in ecological campaigns, programs of moral instruction, and various public initiatives. This demonstrates that Advaita principles extend beyond temple settings and permeate social awareness. In this sense, metaphysical insights merge with ethical responsibilities, sustaining the vision of unity in diversity that lies at the heart of Balinese ideals of harmony and ecological balance.

Balinese Hindu priests (*sulinggih*) also express non-dual ideas, though often using different terminology. Many emphasize that recognizing the true self (*ātman*) is a vital step toward spiritual freedom. As one priest explained during an interview: "*Ati sane saking sang paramātman punika dados cihna manusa sane utama, sane ngidang ngerasaang satyam*," which can be translated as the realization of the divine self, a noble individual who is able to experience truth. Such teachings affirm that the essence of Advaita—self-realization and detachment—remains central within Balinese religiosity.

Applying a hermeneutic lens also makes it possible to bridge classical Indian scriptures with present-day Balinese religious life. When texts and rituals are seen as part of a continuous process of reinterpretation, it becomes clear how Advaita Vedānta adjusts to shifting social and cultural realities. In the midst of globalization, environmental challenges, and the commodification of spirituality, Advaita provides not only a timeless metaphysical vision but also a flexible ethical foundation that supports resilience and spiritual depth in Balinese society.

Research Method

This research employs a qualitative hermeneutic framework to investigate how Advaita Vedānta is articulated and reinterpreted within Balinese Hindu thought. Following Hans-Georg Gadamer, interpretation is treated as a dialogical process shaped by cultural and historical horizons (Gadamer, 2004). Hermeneutic steps were applied to specific Balinese *lontar* texts through close reading, comparison of semantic layers, and analysis of symbolic vocabulary in relation to lived ritual practices. Primary philosophical sources—*Tattwa Jñāna*, *Bhuwana Kosa*, and locally transmitted commentaries—were selected based on their explicit treatment of metaphysical concepts such as *ātman*, *paramārtha*, and *advaita*. Rituals displaying non-dual cosmological symbolism were included when they demonstrated conceptual continuity with these textual sources.

Interpretations were validated through methodological triangulation involving: (1) textual exegesis of *lontar*, (2) cross-textual comparison between Balinese and Advaita Vedānta sources, and (3) participant observation of ritual forms without eliciting verbal explanations. This approach ensures that meanings derived from the texts are corroborated through consistent symbolic structures found in ritual actions and material expressions, rather than remaining confined to theoretical abstraction. Through this combined strategy, the study demonstrates how metaphysical ideas are embodied, negotiated, and sustained within Balinese Hindu cosmology and communal life (Patton, 2015; Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

Advaita Vedānta is one of the most influential schools of Hindu philosophy, focusing on the principle of non-duality (*advaita*) between the ultimate reality (Brahman) and the true self (*Ātman*). This school was systematized by Śrī Śaṅkarācārya in the 8th century CE, who reinterpreted sacred texts such as the Upaniṣads, Bhagavadgītā, and Brahmasūtra through a monistic lens. He taught that “Brahman is the only reality, the world is *māyā* (illusion), and the individual self is not different from Brahman” (Deutsch, 1980, p. 11). To promote these teachings, he established four maṭhas (monasteries) across India.

Central to Advaita Vedānta are five key concepts: *Brahman*, *Ātman*, *māyā*, *mokṣa*, and *jīvanmukti*. Brahman is described as the absolute, formless, changeless reality (*nirguṇa*), while *Ātman* is the inner self, ultimately identical to Brahman. The illusion of separation is caused by *māyā*, which creates the appearance of multiplicity. Liberation (*mokṣa*) occurs when one realizes this essential unity, and *jīvanmukti* is the state of being liberated while still alive—living with full awareness of oneness with Brahman (Sengupta, 2012).

The foundation of Advaita Vedānta lies in the *prasthāna traya*: the Upaniṣads, Bhagavadgītā, and Brahmasūtra. The Chāndogya Upaniṣad (6.8.7) contains the phrase “*Tat tvam asi*” (“Thou art That”), affirming the unity of self and Brahman. The Bhagavadgītā teaches that the wise see the same *Ātman* in all beings (5.18), while the Brahmasūtra—compiled by Bādarāyaṇa and interpreted by Śaṅkara—begins with “*athāto brahma jijñāsā*,” a call to seek Brahman as the supreme knowledge (Radhakrishnan & Moore, 1957). Although deeply metaphysical, Advaita also supports a practical path of spiritual realization, urging transformation of consciousness. While rooted in India, its principles have influenced regions like Bali, where Advaita’s non-dual values appear in local texts, rituals, and symbols.

Balinese Hinduism has evolved into a rich, contextual tradition supported by the *lontar* manuscript culture. One key example is the *Bhuana Kosa* text, available through *Kalangwan: Jurnal Pendidikan Agama, Bahasa dan Sastra*, which outlines a cosmology based on *Tattwa*

Rudra and the *Panca Mahā Bhūta*. It reflects a worldview where macrocosm and microcosm are interconnected (“The Concept of Hindu Cosmology in the Bhuana Kosa Text,” 2022, p. xx).

The dualistic tension between *sekala* (visible) and *niskala* (invisible), as well as the concept of *rwa bhineda* (complementary opposites), is explored in a study on the Pararem Gering Agung’s customary response to the COVID-19 pandemic. It emphasizes how Balinese people understand reality as both physical and spiritual (Sari et al., 2022, p. 45). These concepts are also evident in the arts. For example, traditional Kamasan paintings use narrative to visually depict *sekala–niskala* duality (Purwita, 2021), and Wayang Kamasan costume motifs reflect both adherence to tradition and artistic creativity (Mudarahayu et al., 2021, p. 88).

The principle of Tri Hita Karana is a philosophical expression of non-duality, where ethical relations with the divine, other beings, and the natural world reflect a unified ontological ground rather than separate spheres of duty. Though not often explored in detailed textual studies, ethnographic evidence shows this philosophy lives in practice (Sari et al., 2022, p. 50). The phrase *tat tvam asi*, while from the Upaniṣads, has become a core ethical value in Bali. Though academic documentation is limited, it frequently appears in education, environmental discourse, and community ethics, expressing oneness with all beings. The spiritual figures of *sulinggih* and *pinandita* (Balinese Hindu priests) are key to preserving and transmitting Balinese philosophy. They teach through ritual, storytelling, and direct experience, emphasizing intuition over dogma. This approach allows Balinese Hinduism to remain open and adaptable, deeply rooted in lived experience.

To interpret these practices and symbols, philosophical hermeneutics is relevant. Hans-Georg Gadamer, in *Truth and Method*, sees understanding not as objective discovery but as an interaction shaped by history and tradition. Meaning arises in the fusion of the interpreter’s and the text’s “horizons” (Gadamer, 1960/1989, p. 306). He argues that prejudices are not errors but part of our inherited worldview (p. 301). Paul Ricoeur complements this by emphasizing hermeneutics as the bridge between symbolic language and self-understanding. He highlights a dialectical process involving distance from and return to the text with new insight. For Ricoeur, understanding evolves through interaction between original context and present interpretation. Applied to Balinese Hinduism, these hermeneutical tools treat rituals and symbols as “analogue texts,” revealing meaning through dialogue between tradition and personal insight. This enables a meaningful comparison between Advaita Vedānta and Balinese practices, honoring both their uniqueness and shared values.

Convergence and Divergence between Advaita Vedānta and Balinese Hinduism

The dialogue between Advaita Vedānta and Balinese Hindu philosophy demonstrates both convergence in metaphysical orientation and divergence in ritual-theological expression. Advaita’s central doctrine—“Brahman is the only reality, the world is *māyā*, and the individual self is not different from Brahman” (Deutsch, 1980, p. 11)—finds resonance in Balinese *tattwa* literature. Texts such as *Tattwa Jñāna* and *Bhuwana Kosa* articulate an ontological unity between *ātmā* and *paramātmā*, understood through the framework of *paramārtha* as the ultimate, non-phenomenal truth (Radhakrishnan & Moore, 1957; “The Concept of Hindu Cosmology in the Bhuana Kosa Text,” 2022). Ethical manifestations of this non-dualism appear in the Balinese use of the Upaniṣadic expression *tat tvam asi* as a civic-spiritual principle, emphasizing care for others and the environment as lived awareness of oneness.

Yet divergence is evident in theological lineage and ritual embodiment. While Advaita emphasizes *nirguṇa Brahman*—absolute, attributeless reality—Balinese Hinduism is largely shaped by *Śaiva Siddhānta*, where divinity is ritually expressed through attributes, forms,

symbolic offerings, and hierarchical manifestations of *Íswara*, *Siwa*, and *Rudra*. Consequently, non-duality is not abstracted into metaphysical speculation but performed through material symbols that function as “analogue texts” (Ricoeur, 1974), enabling philosophical meaning to emerge through ritual enactment. This difference reveals not contradiction but a hermeneutic creativity—a “fusion of horizons” (Gadamer, 1989, p. 306), in which imported metaphysical concepts are continually reinterpreted through Balinese cultural embodiment.

Traces of Advaita Vedānta in Balinese Hindu Texts

In the *Tattwa Jñāna* manuscript, the structure of *tattwa* teachings is explained systematically, including *cetana* (consciousness) and *acetana* (non-consciousness), as well as the process of emanation from *Paramaśiva* to the individual *jīvatman*. These teachings encompass the concepts of *Pañca Mahā Bhūta* and *Yoga* as means of attaining *mokṣa*, revealing that individual consciousness (*Ātman*) is a manifestation of *Brahman* (Harsananda, 2021, p. 189).

Paramaśiva is the highest reality in Balinese Hindu philosophy, especially in the teachings of *Tattwa Jñāna* and *Śaiva Siddhānta*. He is described as the ultimate essence—formless (*niṣkala*), attributeless (*nirguṇa*), immutable, unmoving, and eternal. He transcends all dualities and limitations, including time, space, causality, and even the mind itself. As the source of all things, *Paramaśiva* cannot be grasped by the five senses or ordinary reason, but can only be realized through mystical experience or pure awareness (*jñāna*). Though unattainable by ordinary means, *Paramaśiva* is not a passive void, but a void filled with the light of consciousness (*prakāśa*) that supports the entire universe. In Balinese spiritual experience, *Paramaśiva* is present as the source of life and the ultimate goal of self-unification (*mokṣa*)—He is the eternal silence that transcends all names and forms. The *Tattwa Jñāna* text states:

Parama Śiwa tan rūpa, tan calita, tan kampya, tan gata, tan srava, tan mula, tan gati, tan ādya, tan antya, eka sthāna tan calita, śānta acala nitya. Sarva loka vyāpī, sarva jagat saṁvāhya, sarva kāla atīta, nitya śāśvata.

Translation:

Parama Śiwa is formless, unmoving, unshaken, does not depart, does not flow, has no origin, no destination, no beginning, and no end. He remains in one place, unshifting, serene, immovable, and eternal. He pervades the entire world, sustains the whole universe, transcends all time; He is eternal and everlasting (Manuskrip Iontar Bali, Koleksi Yayasan Bali Kuna)

In *Tattwa Jñāna*, *Parama Śiwa* is described as the supreme, formless, and eternal reality—beyond motion, time, space, and attributes. He is not a personal deity but pure, *nirguṇa* consciousness that pervades and sustains the universe, aligning with the non-dual goal of *mokṣa* in Balinese Hinduism (Dinas Kebudayaan Provinsi Bali, 1994, p. 15). This understanding reflects the *Śaiva Siddhānta* view that Śiwa is untouched by *māyā* and is the existential foundation of all being (Bagus, 1991). A verse in *Tattwa Jñāna*—“Ātmanah svayam utpanam sva liṅgam”—emphasizes the Ātman’s pure nature, free from illusion, echoing the Advaita doctrine that Ātman is Brahman (Harsananda, 2021). The doctrine of *Vivartavāda*, which sees the world as an illusory appearance of Brahman, is mirrored in Balinese *Iontars* that portray reality as impermanent, resonating with Gauḍapāda’s *ajātivāda*—the idea that nothing is ever truly born (Puligandla, 1997). Similarly, *Bhuwana Kosa* expresses a monistic cosmology in which the universe cyclically emerges from and dissolves into Brahman through *Bhatāra Śiwa*, reflecting a worldview consistent with Advaita Vedānta (Sura, 1999/2013).

*Sang Hyang Brahman ika tan kadi mabuin, tan kadi mabulus, tan kadi mangrawit,
tan kadi mapapa, tan kadi mamisah, ika madyānta tan kawan, tan kawruhan ri
tattwa, sang paramārtha.*

Translation:

Sang Hyang Brahman is not something that is born, not something that enters or exits, not something that undergoes process, not something that unites or separates, without beginning or end, and unknowable through ordinary knowledge; this is the ultimate truth (*paramārtha*) (Sura, 1999/2013)

This verse explains that Brahman, as presented in *Bhuwana Kosa*, is not a phenomenal entity: He is unborn (*tan mabuin*), undying, and unchanging. He transcends dualities such as entry–exit or union–separation, being both transcendent and immanent, reflecting the perspective of Advaita Vedānta (Suamba, 2020). The experience of the ultimate truth (*paramārtha*)—not intellectual knowledge (*tan kawruhan ri tattwa*)—is the only way to realize Brahman. In the teachings of *Bhuwana Kosa*, the entire cosmos is born from Sang Hyang Brahman through the manifestation of Śiwa and returns to Him through *pralaya*, forming a sacred cycle (*rta*) that confirms the non-duality of Brahman and the universe—a unity of existence beneath all temporal changes.

Although Śaṅkarācārya is not explicitly mentioned in Balinese *lontar* texts, his teachings are implicitly present through the principles of Advaita: that Ātman and Brahman are one, and liberation is attained through knowledge of *nirguṇa* Brahman (Mudra, 2010). This aligns with Śaṅkara’s teachings on Mahāvākyas such as *tat tvam asi* as means to realize the identity of self and Brahman. The understanding of Brahman as *Sarvavikriyā-rahita* (free from all actions) is also reflected in *Bhuwana Kosa* and *Tattwa Jñāna*, where both epistemic and phenomenal elements are regarded as aspects of Brahman, untouched by action—consistent with Śaṅkara’s interpretation of the Ātman as actionless (*kriyāśrayatvān*).

Another Balinese *lontar* text that explicitly discusses the identity between Brahman and Ātman is *Sanghyang Mahājñāna*. This text presents a philosophical dialogue between Sang Kumāra and Bhatāra Guru about true self-awareness (*Ātman*) as an inseparable part of the supreme reality (*Brahman*) (Windya, Sukayasa, & Wirawan, 2022). In the opening section of this text, Ajñāna (ignorance) and Māyā are analyzed as barriers (obscured consciousness), while Ātman/Brahman is described as the light of awareness that transcends all—“*tan kadi mowis, tan kadi manggalesa*” (not born, not perished; similar diction to *Bhuwana Kosa*). The ultimate goal is to attain *mokṣa* (liberation), formulated as the complete union of Ātman and Brahman—the realization of their essential oneness. *Sanghyang Mahājñāna 56* states:

*Kamalaṁ ca prāṇalaṁ ca, tiktaṁ īśvara eva ca,
śarīratane divye tatra sthāpya Maheśvaraḥ.*

Translation:

The lotus (*kamala*), the vital energy channels (*prāṇala*), and the bitter taste (*tikta*) — all are manifestations of Śiwa. In this sacred temple of the body (*śarīra-āyatana divye*), Maheśvara resides (Windya, 2021)

The *Sanghyang Mahājñāna (56)* presents a *Tantric Śaiva* view of the body as sacred. Bodily elements such as the lotus (*chakra*), *prāṇala* (energy channels), and the bitter taste (*tikta*, symbolizing spiritual austerity) are seen as manifestations of Śiwa as Īśvara. The body is called *śarīra-āyatana divye*, the divine temple where Maheśvara resides. This reflects a non-dual understanding of spirituality where body and consciousness are united. Realizing the body as a sacred mandala, where *ātman* and Śiwa meet, becomes the path to liberation (*mokṣa*) (Windya, 2021).

Other Balinese lontar texts also contain teachings aligned with Advaita Vedānta, though the term is not explicitly used. Sarasamuscaya emphasizes *Ātman* as the ontological basis of existence: “If there is no Dharma of the *Ātman*, there is no past, no future, no time or beings” (Sarasamuscaya, sloka 248), suggesting the world depends on the *Ātman* (Darmayasa, 2004, p. 97). Jñāna Siddhānta teaches that *mokṣa* is achieved through knowledge (*jñāna*) of the unity between *Ātman* and Brahman: “*Ātma* itself is... Brahman” (Sudharta, 1993, p. 45). Similarly, Taturan Bhatāra Rsi Agastya affirms that union with Brahman is only possible through perfected knowledge (*jñāna yoga*) (Suarjana, 2005, p. 88).

In Tattwa Rare Angon, the *Ātman* is called the true inner Guru, inaccessible externally: “The true Guru is the *ātman* within you” (Parwita, 2012, p. 73). This teaching highlights inner realization as the key to truth. Together, these texts reveal a fusion of Tantric, Vedāntic, and Balinese wisdom—emphasizing non-duality, inner realization, and the sacredness of embodied spiritual experience.

Advaita in Religious and Symbolic Practice in Bali

In Balinese religious life, the non-dualistic philosophy of Advaita Vedānta is reflected in the awareness of unity between the self (*ātman*), nature, and God (Brahman). This idea is grounded in the teaching of *Tat Tvam Asi*—“Thou art That”—a *mahāvākya* from the *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* (VI.8.7), which teaches that the essence of all beings is one and the same: Brahman. In Bali, this teaching is not limited to abstract metaphysics but is applied in daily life, shaping the worldview, social ethics, and spiritual practices of the people (Suamba, 2020). Rituals such as *pitra yadnya* (ancestral rites), temple architecture, and the empty *padmasana* shrine all reflect this non-dual awareness. Through meditation, *tapa* (austerities), and *japa* (sacred chanting), Balinese spirituality recognizes not only the diversity of forms but also the oneness behind them.

In ceremonies like *mebayuh* (ritual purification), *metirta yatra* (pilgrimage), and *pitra yadnya*, the teaching of *Tat Tvam Asi* guides the attitude of reverence toward all beings and elements, recognizing them as expressions of one divine essence. Worship is not directed to separate deities alone, but to the underlying unity present in ancestors, nature, and the cosmos. This affirms that sanctity is not limited to divine realms but is present in every aspect of life (Bagus, 1991). The teaching of *Tat Tvam Asi* becomes the soul of rituals and an ethical principle that governs interpersonal and ecological relationships.

This ethical view is closely linked to *Tri Hita Karana*—the harmony between humans and God, other people, and nature. Harming the environment or living beings is seen as violating the same *ātman* that lives in all forms. Thus, *Tat Tvam Asi* serves not only as a moral foundation but also as an ecological and spiritual guideline (Ardhana & Surata, 2015). In this way, Advaita shapes not only inner awareness but also external action and responsibility.

Education in Bali, both within the family and in *pasraman* (religious schools), plays a central role in transmitting these values. Children are taught Upaniṣadic verses, the principle of *sarvam khalvidam brahma* (“all this is Brahman”), and ethical teachings that promote unity between the self and the universe. Practices such as *karma yoga*, *seva* (selfless service), and dialogue help students realize the divine in all beings. As Swami Vivekananda taught, “Service to humanity is service to God” (Vivekananda, 2005). In Bali, this is embodied in social values like *gotong royong* (mutual cooperation), *karya bakti* (community service), and temple care.

Balinese cosmology also reflects Advaita through symbolic spatial design, where the universe (macrocosm) and human self (microcosm) are unified. Everything originates from Brahman, and this understanding is built into sacred structures. The *mandala* is a key symbol in Balinese temples, representing cosmic order. It integrates the five elements—fire, water, earth, air, and

space—into a balanced whole that centers around the divine source, Brahman. This sacred center symbolizes the formless, attributeless Brahman (*nirguṇa*), yet present in all forms (*nāmarūpa*). As stated in the *Lontar Bhuana Kosa*: “Sang hyang sūkṣma tan kadyaning angayahang, hana tan hana” — the subtle one cannot be imagined; it both exists and does not exist (Suamba, 2020).

Another symbol, *Catur Loka Pala*, represents the four cardinal guardians—Isvara (east), Brahma (south), Mahadeva (west), and Vishnu (north). Though distinct, they symbolize the unity of consciousness. Diversity in directions, roles, and energies is understood as a reflection of one source, in line with *Tat Tvam Asi* (Chāndogya Upaniṣad VI.8.7). Thus, dualities like light and dark, fire and water, or masculine and feminine are reconciled through the vision of spiritual unity.

The *Padmasana*, the highest shrine in Balinese temples, further reinforces this philosophy. It is intentionally left empty to represent *Brahman nirākāra*—the formless God beyond image or attribute. Unlike other shrines that contain deity images (*pratima*), the Padmasana speaks through silence and space, pointing to the indwelling divine consciousness (*adyātma tattwa*) as the true essence of all beings (Ardhana & Surata, 2015).

Temple architecture itself embodies the spiritual journey. The division into *nista mandala* (outer zone), *madya mandala* (middle), and *utama mandala* (innermost) reflects the path from the profane toward the sacred. This spatial progression is a symbolic map of transcendence—from worldly attachment toward realization of unity with Brahman. Ardika (2018) explains that temple zoning reflects Hindu values of spiritual hierarchy and transcendence. The temple, therefore, becomes not only a place of worship but also a mirror of the self—a place for inner transformation.

Temple orientation also aligns with the principle of *Bhuana Agung* and *Bhuana Alit*—macrocosm and microcosm—further reinforcing that the universe and self are one reality. Yudiantini and Jones (2015) note that Balinese sacred architecture is designed to harmonize body and universe, embodying *Tat Tvam Asi*. Awareness of directions (such as *kaja–kelod*, *kangin–kauh*) is not only geographic but deeply spiritual.

Even decorative symbols in temples hold deep meaning. *Karang Bhoma* represents subconscious protection, *kalpavriksha* symbolizes spiritual abundance, and *nagabanda* reflects the binding force of energy. These motifs remind worshippers that cosmic forces are also present within. As the *Bṛihadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad* (I.4.10) declares: *Aham Brahmāsmi*—“I am Brahman.” This realization, the heart of Advaita, is experienced through architecture, symbolism, and ritual. In essence, Advaita Vedānta in Bali is not confined to abstract philosophy but is lived through ritual, ethics, architecture, and education. The Balinese religious system translates the vision of non-duality into symbolic and communal practices that nurture harmony, unity, and spiritual realization in everyday life (Eiseman, 1990; Lansing, 2006; Hobart et al., 2001).

Advaita and the Socio-Cultural Consciousness of Balinese Society

In Balinese spiritual and cultural life, the concept of *rwa bhineda*—the coexistence of opposites like light and dark, good and bad—is central to how people understand the world. These dualities are not seen as contradictory but as complementary forces that together form harmony. This aligns with Advaita Vedānta’s core teaching that dualities exist only at the level of *vyavahāra satya* (relative reality), while at the level of *pāramārthika satya* (absolute truth), everything is one: Brahman (Deutsch, 1973). This worldview encourages Balinese people to see differences not as conflict, but as part of a greater unity that must be maintained.

This understanding is reflected in social and spiritual systems that prioritize harmony over domination. In rituals and symbols—such as temple layouts aligned with mountain–sea (*kaja–kelod*) and east–west (*kangin–kauh*) axes, or offerings made with dual elements like red–white, water–fire, and male–female—the visible diversity points toward one sacred centre. This center represents *Brahman nirguṇa*, the formless ultimate reality behind all expressions (Maharsi, 2015). Thus, Advaita Vedānta becomes a living principle, embedded in everyday Balinese culture.

Socially, this perspective fosters values of tolerance, mutual respect, and peaceful coexistence. Eiseman (1990) notes that Balinese harmony “does not come from an attempt to homogenize differences, but from accepting plurality as part of the cosmic order.” This shows how Advaita becomes a foundation for social inclusivity, where diversity is understood as a reflection of a shared essence. It also supports social unity in the face of modern challenges such as globalization, helping maintain cultural identity through philosophical depth.

Advaita is also closely tied to *Tri Hita Karana*—the philosophy of harmony between humans, God, and nature. All three are seen as manifestations of Brahman, meaning that caring for each is a spiritual act. In *parahyangan* (human–God), rituals and ceremonies express devotion to the Divine as present in all forms. Ardika and Yudhistira (2024) explain that sacred rituals in Bali foster environmental awareness because spirituality is deeply tied to nature. *Pawongan* (human–human) reflects the belief that every individual carries divine essence. Practices like *gotong royong* (mutual cooperation), village rituals, and community work are not only social norms but spiritual expressions. Utama & Yamin (2025) show how even local credit systems in villages apply *Tri Hita Karana*, ensuring that economic activities reflect social and environmental responsibility.

In *palemahan* (human–nature), nature is honored as part of the sacred. The *Subak* irrigation system, a UNESCO heritage, is a prime example of how Balinese farmers manage resources through both ecological and religious principles. Yasa and Sugriwa (2025) highlight how energy projects also adopt *Tri Hita Karana* to combine ethical, ecological, and spiritual sustainability. From an Advaita perspective, honoring these three relationships is honoring Brahman in its various forms. The Upaniṣadic teaching *sarvam khalvidam brahma*—“all this is indeed Brahman”—encourages Balinese society to integrate spirituality, social ethics, and environmental responsibility into one unified awareness.

Hermeneutic Interpretation of Advaita Vedānta in Contemporary Balinese Reality

In contemporary Bali, Advaita Vedānta is no longer restricted to the study of classical scriptures but is interpreted through direct lived realities. Sindhu Gitananda and Yudabakti (2019) emphasize that *pratyakṣa*—knowledge derived from immediate experience—functions as a central hermeneutical method. Values rooted in Vedānta are transmitted through ritual practice, formal education, and communal engagement, thereby embedding Advaita within everyday life rather than leaving it as an abstract philosophical framework.

Within *pasraman* (Hindu schools), Balinese students are introduced to teachings such as *Aham Brahmāsmi* and *Tat Tvam Asi* as foundations for character formation, yogic discipline, and ethical conduct. Textual study is approached less as rigid doctrine and more as a dialogical process inviting reflection and reinterpretation. This dynamic approach allows Advaita to remain both adaptable and meaningful in responding to contemporary issues such as rampant consumerism, crises of identity, and social fragmentation.

One of Advaita’s strengths lies in offering individuals a way to confront existential unease by rooting identity in universal consciousness rather than in external expectations. Ambarnuari and Harsananda (2021) affirm that “everything that exists in this world is God,” suggesting that

yoga and self-inquiry become practical means of realizing this inner unity. In the Balinese context, where globalization risks turning spirituality into a market commodity, Advaita provides an authentic anchor that protects cultural revitalization from superficiality (Tatkala, 2021).

Numerous spiritual centers are active in fostering Advaita-based practices. Ashram Gandhi Puri in Klungkung encourages meditation, austerities (*tapas*), and mindful living as pathways of non-dual realization. Samyama in Ubud refers to yoga as a “pilgrimage of the soul,” explicitly grounded in non-dual awareness (Samyama Retreat Center, 2018). More recently, the International Vedanta Society inaugurated an ashram in 2024, providing retreats and practical teaching rooted in Advaita philosophy (International Vedanta Society, 2024), thus linking global Vedāntic movements with Balinese settings.

Another example is Pasraman Bali Eling Spirit in Ubud, which offers Yoga Alliance–accredited programs that integrate the *Bhagavadgītā*, the Upaniṣads, and the *Yoga Sūtras* of Patañjali with teachings on Dharma and life mastery. Such initiatives enable both Balinese youth and international practitioners to approach Advaita as a deeply personal spiritual path while remaining embedded in Balinese cultural values (Pasraman Bali Eling Spirit). This evolving pattern illustrates how younger generations are not merely passive recipients of religious traditions but are actively re-engaging them through meditation, contemplation, and ethical practices inspired by Advaita Vedānta.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that Advaita Vedānta continues to occupy a vital and adaptive position within Balinese religion and culture. While its foundations lie in classical Indian philosophy, its non-dual vision resonates locally through concepts such as *rwa bhineda*, *Tri Hita Karana*, and diverse ritual expressions. At the same time, Advaita offers ethical direction for present challenges, contributing to interfaith dialogue, environmental spirituality, and a renewed awareness of divine immanence in daily life. Its influence is especially evident in Bali’s ecological consciousness and in contemporary movements surrounding yoga, meditation, and *pasraman* education.

To consolidate Advaita as an integral part of Bali’s spiritual heritage, further interdisciplinary research remains crucial. Combining philological analysis with anthropological and phenomenological inquiry—particularly on *tattwa* texts like *Tattwa Jñāna*, *Bhuwana Kosa*, and *Tuturan Bhatāra Rsi Agastya*—would help clarify how non-duality is locally interpreted and enacted. Likewise, Hindu education systems could embed Advaita more substantially, not just through doctrinal instruction but by cultivating contemplative practices such as *svādhyāya*, meditation, and *jñāna yoga*. In an era marked by fragmentation and uncertainty, Advaita carries a universal lesson: genuine fulfillment arises from realizing the inseparability of Ātman and Brahman. This vision calls individuals to live with peace, mindfulness, and inclusivity, firmly rooted in the wisdom of unity.

Future studies may ask: How do Balinese rituals embody non-dual epistemology? How is Advaita reshaped by tourism, digital media, and the global yoga movement? In what ways can Advaita inform environmental law or interfaith policy in Indonesia? Likewise, Hindu education systems could embed Advaita more substantially, not just through doctrinal instruction but by cultivating contemplative practices such as *svādhyāya*, meditation, and *jñāna yoga*. In an era marked by fragmentation and uncertainty, Advaita carries a universal lesson: genuine fulfillment arises from realizing the inseparability of Ātman and Brahman.

This research is limited primarily to textual interpretation and philosophical analysis, supported by selective ethnographic references. It does not yet incorporate extensive fieldwork across various Balinese communities, nor does it measure the impact of Advaita-based education

empirically. Moreover, the study focuses more on Hindu textual and ritual theory rather than socio-political or economic forces that may also influence religious interpretation. Future research should therefore expand toward broader ethnographic sampling, interdisciplinary methodologies, and empirical evaluation of Advaita-based educational and ecological models.

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